

EQUIVALENT MATERIAL FOR THE ANALYSIS OF LAMINATED AND SANDWICH STRUCTURES

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This paper presents a process for the analysis of laminated or sandwich plates and shells, based on the substitution of the real constitutive material by a fictitious equivalent material, the properties of which are determined from the laminated or sandwich properties. This process applied to the finite element method allows to use the classical finite elements in a slightly modified form and avoids resorting to special finite elements for laminated and sandwich structures. The analysis can be applied to the classical and extended laminated or sandwich structures, i.e. structures with the following generalized elastic behaviour :

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{N} \\ \mathbf{M} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{A} & \mathbf{B} \\ \mathbf{B} & \mathbf{D} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^o \\ \mathbf{K} \end{Bmatrix} \quad \{\mathbf{Q}\} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{d} \end{bmatrix} \{\boldsymbol{\Gamma}\}$$

where \mathbf{N} , \mathbf{M} and \mathbf{Q} are the in-plane forces, bending moments and shear forces, $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^o$, \mathbf{K} and $\boldsymbol{\Gamma}$ are the membrane strains, curvatures and shearing strains, \mathbf{A} , \mathbf{B} , \mathbf{D} and \mathbf{d} are the in-plane, coupling, bending and shear stiffnesses. The analysis is based on a kinematic and material similarity between these structures and the three dimensional finite element with two nodes in the thickness and elastic stiffnesses varying parabolically along the thickness. With well chosen stiffnesses for its constitutive material, this element can reproduce exactly the behaviour of any laminated or sandwich structure, including coupling and shear effects. This theoretical result was assessed by numerous numerical tests performed with a complete three dimensional finite element and an Ahmad three dimensional finite element, both using the method presented here. The results show a complete agreement with a special laminated and sandwich finite element program, which demonstrates that the present study provides an effective low cost process to convert a classical finite element program into a laminated and sandwich finite element program.

INTRODUCTION

The so-called *classical laminated plate theory* was initiated in the well-known works of Lekhnitskii [1] (1956), Pister and Dong [2] (1959), Reissner and Stavsky [3] (1961). These pioneering works, based on the Kirchhoff-Love hypothesis, were further extended to shells and to the treatment of transverse shear effects for plates and shells by numerous authors (see textbooks on the mechanics of composite materials, such as [4], for references). These problems are indeed not yet settled and are still receiving much attention. However, most of the theories have in common the relations between the generalized forces and the generalized strains, usually written in the following matrix form :

$$\begin{aligned} \begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{N} \\ \mathbf{M} \end{Bmatrix} &= \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{A} & \mathbf{B} \\ \mathbf{B} & \mathbf{D} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^0 \\ \mathbf{K} \end{Bmatrix} \\ \mathbf{Q} &= \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{d} \end{bmatrix} \boldsymbol{\Gamma} \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbf{N}, \mathbf{M}, \mathbf{Q}$ are the in-plane forces, bending moments and shear forces, and $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^0, \mathbf{K}, \boldsymbol{\Gamma}$ are the membrane strains, curvatures and shearing strains. The quantities $\mathbf{A}, \mathbf{B}, \mathbf{D}$ and \mathbf{d} are the in-plane stiffnesses, the coupling stiffnesses, the bending stiffnesses and the shear stiffnesses. In the various theories, the formulas expressing these stiffnesses from the properties of the laminas show some slight differences, which will not be discussed here. Further, the constitutive relations (1) are also valid for sandwich structures, with adequate formulas for the stiffnesses. So, in the sequel, we will simply retain the equations (1) as a general starting point in the analysis of laminated and sandwich structures.

The differential equations governing the equilibrium of laminated and sandwich structures are consequently composed of the equations defining the generalized strains $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^0, \mathbf{K}$ and $\boldsymbol{\Gamma}$, the equilibrium equations for generalized forces \mathbf{N}, \mathbf{M} and \mathbf{Q} , and Eq. (1). No general closed-form solution can be derived for these partial differential equations. Accordingly, numerical techniques are widely used for their solution, especially the finite element method. Numerous plate and shell finite elements developed for laminated and sandwich structures are available in specialized programs. However, many general purpose structural analysis programs do not have such finite elements, or have some with limited capabilities with respect to general anisotropy, coupling effects, shear effects, etc. . The present paper describes a method of converting the three dimensional finite elements at disposal in every large program into a laminated or sandwich plate and shell element.

THEORETICAL ANALYSIS

The process is based upon the similarity in laminated or sandwich structure and some modified three dimensional structure. This property is clearly revealed by a comparison of the strain energy of these two types of structure. For sake of simplicity, the analysis will be developed in full only for the Mindlin-type laminated plate theory, from which the case of other laminated or sandwich plate theories, as well as the case of shells can be easily derived.

The analysis requires a special perspicuity in notation, so the complete tensorial index notation, which is unequivocal if rather cumbersome, will be used. The cartesian coordinate system is formed of the axes x_1 and x_2 in the middle surface of the laminate and the axis x_3 normal to this surface. *Greek* indices take the values 1 and 2 only, whereas *Latin* indices take the values 1, 2 and 3. Consequently, the summation convention for repeated (dummy) indices applies from 1 to 2 for Greek indices and from 1 to 3 for Latin indices.

The Mindlin-type displacements in the plate are :

$$\begin{cases} u_\alpha = u_\alpha^m(x_1, x_2) + x_3 \psi_\alpha(x_1, x_2) \\ u_3 = w(x_1, x_2) \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

$$\quad (3)$$

where u_α^m are the mean in-plane displacements, ψ_α the rotations and w the deflection. The generalized strains are consequently expressed by the following formulas :

$$\begin{cases} 2\varepsilon_{\alpha\beta}^m = \frac{\partial u_\alpha^m}{\partial x_\beta} + \frac{\partial u_\beta^m}{\partial x_\alpha} \\ 2K_{\alpha\beta} = \frac{\partial \psi_\alpha}{\partial x_\beta} + \frac{\partial \psi_\beta}{\partial x_\alpha} \\ \Gamma_\alpha = \psi_\alpha + \frac{\partial w}{\partial x_\alpha} \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

The generalized stress-strain relations of Eq. 1 are then written :

$$\begin{cases} N_{\alpha\beta} = A_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta}^M \varepsilon_{\gamma\delta}^m + B_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta}^M K_{\gamma\delta} \\ M_{\alpha\beta} = B_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta}^M \varepsilon_{\gamma\delta}^m + D_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta}^M K_{\gamma\delta} \\ Q_\alpha = d_{\alpha\beta}^M \Gamma_\beta \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

where the superscript M holds for "Mindlin-type theory". The appropriate formulas for the generalized stiffnesses will not be detailed here.

Finally, the strain energy (per unit surface of the plate) is given by :

$$\phi^M = 1/2 (A_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta}^M \varepsilon_{\alpha\beta}^m \varepsilon_{\gamma\delta}^m + 2B_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta}^M \varepsilon_{\alpha\beta}^m K_{\gamma\delta} + D_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta}^M K_{\alpha\beta} K_{\gamma\delta} + d_{\alpha\beta}^M \Gamma_\alpha \Gamma_\beta) \quad (6)$$

Consider now the displacements used in the well-known three-dimensional isoparametric finite element with two nodes in the x_3 direction (Fig. 1) :

$$u_i = L^+(z)u_i^+(x_1, x_2) + L^-(z)u_i^-(x_1, x_2) \quad (7)$$

where $z = 2x_3/h$ is the reduced transverse coordinate, and $L^+ = (1+z)/2$ and $L^- = (1-z)/2$ are the classical linear shape functions.

Figure 1

Eq. (7) defines a transversely linear field of displacements expressed with the displacements of the upper surface u_i^+ and of lower surface u_i^- . An alternate form for this displacement field can be easily derived :

$$u_i = u_i^0(x_1, x_2) + z u_i^1(x_1, x_2) \quad (8)$$

with the following values :

$$\begin{cases} u_i^0 = (u_i^+ + u_i^-)/2 \\ u_i^1 = (u_i^+ - u_i^-)/2 \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

The corresponding strains have the form :

$$\epsilon_{ij} = \epsilon_{ij}^0 + z \epsilon_{ij}^1 \quad (10)$$

with the following values :

$$\begin{cases} 2\epsilon_{\alpha\beta}^0 = \frac{\partial u_\alpha^0}{\partial x_\beta} + \frac{\partial u_\beta^0}{\partial x_\alpha} \\ 2\epsilon_{\alpha\beta}^1 = \frac{\partial u_\alpha^1}{\partial x_\beta} + \frac{\partial u_\beta^1}{\partial x_\alpha} \\ 2\epsilon_{\alpha 3}^0 = 2u_\alpha^1/h + \frac{\partial u_3^0}{\partial x_\alpha} \\ 2\epsilon_{\alpha 3}^1 = \frac{\partial u_3^1}{\partial x_\alpha} \\ \epsilon_{33}^0 = 2u_3^1/h \\ \epsilon_{33}^1 = 0 \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

From these equations, a wide similarity can be seen between the Mindlin-type plate and the finite element-type plate, with the correspondences listed in Table 1.

Mindlin	u_α^m	ψ_α	w	$\epsilon_{\alpha\beta}^m$	$K_{\alpha\beta}$	Γ_α	†	†
Finite element	u_α^0	$2u_\alpha^1/h$	u_3^0	$\epsilon_{\alpha\beta}^0$	$2\epsilon_{\alpha\beta}^1/h$	$2\epsilon_{\alpha 3}^0$	$\epsilon_{\alpha 3}^1$	ϵ_{33}

† : no corresponding quantity

Table 1 - Kinematic correspondences.

This similarity was noticed from the beginning of the development of the isoparametric finite elements and has been widely used ([5], chap.16). However in the previous works, it has been limited to the above kinematic point of view, and consequently has been usable only for homogeneous (and mainly isotropic) plates and shells. An extension can be made to heterogeneous (laminated or sandwich) structures in the following way.

For the finite element-type plate, the constitutive material is assumed to be orthotropic and to change along the thickness in such a way that its elastic moduli C_{ijkl} are quadratic functions of z . For convenience, instead of the plain formula :

$$C_{ijkl} = \bar{C}_{ijkl}^0 + z \bar{C}_{ijkl}^1 + z^2 \bar{C}_{ijkl}^2 \quad (12)$$

the following form will be retained :

$$C_{ijkl} = N_1(z)C_{ijkl}^1 + N_2(z)C_{ijkl}^2 + N_3(z)C_{ijkl}^3 \quad (13)$$

where :

$$\begin{cases} N_1(z) = (z + \beta)z/(2\beta^2) \\ N_2(z) = (\beta^2 - z^2)/\beta^2 \\ N_3(z) = (z - \beta)z/(2\beta^2) \end{cases} \quad (14)$$

with $\beta = \sqrt{3/5}$.

$+\beta$, 0 and $-\beta$ are three abscissae for the Gauss-Legendre quadrature between -1 and $+1$ with the corresponding weights $5/9$, $8/9$ and $5/9$. The functions $N_k(z)$ are parabolic functions of z which take the value 1 at one of the Gauss abscissae and 0 at the two other abscissae. The choice of these functions is connected with the use of the method presented in this paper in finite element programs. It also provides some facilities for deriving the following formulas.

With such material properties, the strain energy per unit area :

$$\phi = 1/2 \int_{-h/2}^{+h/2} C_{ijkl} \epsilon_{ij} \epsilon_{kl} dx_3 \quad (15)$$

is expressed by the following formulas :

$$\phi = h/2 (A_{ijkl} \epsilon_{ij}^0 \epsilon_{kl}^0 + 2B_{ijkl} \epsilon_{ij}^0 \epsilon_{kl}^1 + D_{ijkl} \epsilon_{ij}^1 \epsilon_{kl}^1) \quad (16)$$

or, in a more detailed form :

$$\begin{aligned} \phi = h/2 (& A_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta} \epsilon_{\alpha\beta}^0 \epsilon_{\gamma\delta}^0 + 2A_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta} \epsilon_{\alpha\beta}^0 \epsilon_{33}^0 + A_{3333} \epsilon_{33}^0 \epsilon_{33}^0 + 4A_{\alpha3\beta3} \epsilon_{\alpha3}^0 \epsilon_{\beta3}^0 \\ & + 2B_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta} \epsilon_{\alpha\beta}^0 \epsilon_{\gamma\delta}^1 + 2B_{\alpha\beta33} \epsilon_{33}^0 \epsilon_{\alpha\beta}^1 + 8B_{\alpha3\beta3} \epsilon_{\alpha3}^0 \epsilon_{\beta3}^1 \\ & + D_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta} \epsilon_{\alpha\beta}^1 \epsilon_{\gamma\delta}^1 + 4D_{\alpha3\beta3} \epsilon_{\alpha3}^1 \epsilon_{\beta3}^1) \quad (17) \end{aligned}$$

The quantities A_{ijkl} , B_{ijkl} and D_{ijkl} have the same dimensions as the moduli C_{ijkl} , and have the values :

$$\begin{cases} A_{ijkl} = 5/18 C_{ijkl}^1 + 4/9 C_{ijkl}^2 + 5/18 C_{ijkl}^3 \\ B_{ijkl} = \sqrt{15}/18 (C_{ijkl}^1 - C_{ijkl}^3) \\ D_{ijkl} = 1/6 (C_{ijkl}^1 + C_{ijkl}^3) \end{cases} \quad (18)$$

These formulas can be inverted, yielding :

$$\begin{cases} C_{ijkl}^1 = 3D_{ijkl} + 9/\sqrt{15} B_{ijkl} \\ C_{ijkl}^2 = 9/4 A_{ijkl} - 15/4 D_{ijkl} \\ C_{ijkl}^3 = 3D_{ijkl} - 9/\sqrt{15} B_{ijkl} \end{cases} \quad (19)$$

From Eq. (18) and (19), it can be noticed that the quadratic variation of the elastic moduli in the thickness produces the most general form for the strain energy (i.e. with arbitrary coefficients, including coupling coefficients B_{ijkl}), or reversely, that the most general form of strain energy completely determines a quadratic

variation of the elastic moduli.

At this point, the similarity with the Mindlin-type plate becomes clear. Comparing the strain energy in the two cases (Eq. (6) and Eq. (17)) and taking into account the kinematic correspondences already established in Table 1, the correspondences for material properties are obtained (Table 2).

Mindlin	$A_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta}^M$	$B_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta}^M$	$D_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta}^M$	$d_{\alpha\beta}^M$
Finite element	$hA_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta}$	$h^2B_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta}/2$	$h^3D_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta}/4$	$hA_{\alpha\beta 33}$

Table 2 - Material correspondences for the Mindlin-type and the finite element-type plates

As for kinematic quantities, some material quantities of the finite element-type plate do not have corresponding quantities in the Mindlin-type plate, namely $A_{\alpha\beta 33}$, A_{3333} , $B_{\alpha\beta 33}$, $B_{\alpha 3\beta 3}$ and $D_{\alpha 3\beta 3}$. However the coefficients $A_{\alpha\beta 33}$, $B_{\alpha\beta 33}$ and $D_{\alpha 3\beta 3}$ cause a coupling between the variables u_α^0 , u_α^1 and u_3^0 on one hand and the variable u_3^1 on the other hand. As this variable u_3^1 and its derivatives $\epsilon_{\alpha 3}^1$ and ϵ_{33}^0 cannot receive useful meanings (see Table 1), it is convenient to put :

$$\begin{cases} A_{\alpha\beta 33} = 0 \\ B_{\alpha\beta 33} = 0 \\ B_{\alpha 3\beta 3} = 0 \end{cases} \quad (20)$$

With these values, the strain energy ϕ can be split in two parts :

$$\phi = \phi_1 + \phi_2 \quad (21)$$

with :

$$\phi_1 = h/2(A_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta} \epsilon_{\alpha\beta}^0 \epsilon_{\gamma\delta}^0 + 2B_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta} \epsilon_{\alpha\beta}^0 \epsilon_{\gamma\delta}^1 + D_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta} \epsilon_{\alpha\beta}^1 \epsilon_{\gamma\delta}^1 + 4A_{\alpha 3\beta 3} \epsilon_{\alpha 3}^0 \epsilon_{\beta 3}^0) \quad (22)$$

and :

$$\phi_2 = h/2(A_{3333} \epsilon_{33}^0 \epsilon_{33}^0 + 4D_{\alpha 3\beta 3} \epsilon_{\alpha 3}^1 \epsilon_{\beta 3}^1) \quad (23)$$

The uncoupling obtained from Eq.(20) is not limited to the expression of the strain energy. As the equilibrium equations for the finite element type plate can be derived from the strain energy using the calculus of variations, it can be concluded that the equilibrium equations can also be split in two disconnected parts, one for the variables which can be associated with corresponding variables of the Mindlin-type theory, and a remaining equation for u_3^1 . These differential equations will not be detailed there, because the finite element method which is used in the present analysis does not need them and starts directly from the expression of the strain energy.

A complete similarity of the two plate theories is then achieved. With the relations given in Table 1 and Table 2, the finite element-type theory reproduces exactly the Mindlin-type theory with an extra variable completely disconnected from the others. Consequently it is possible to define an *equivalent material* for any laminated or sandwich plate. The moduli of this equivalent material, to be used in the finite element type theory, have a quadratic variation in the thickness of the structure.

Some comment and details are useful to state precisely the process of an equivalent material. First, it should be asked whether the quantity ϕ_2 involving the superfluous variable u_3^1 can be simply neglected in the finite element process. As it will be seen later, two types of finite elements can be used, one with variables equal to u_α^0 , u_α^1 and u^0 except for multiplicative factors, the other with variables equal to u_α^0 and u_α^1 : at least in the second element, cancelling ϕ_2 might produce singular stiffness matrices. Consequently, in the sequel, the quantity ϕ_2 will be retained with

arbitrary constants A_{3333} and $D_{\alpha\beta\beta}$.

At this point, some constants remain undetermined by the correspondences, namely B_{3333} , $D_{\alpha\beta\beta}$, $D_{\alpha\beta\beta}$ and D_{3333} . As they do not appear in the formulation, they can receive arbitrary values.

Once the constants A_{ijkl} , B_{ijkl} and D_{ijkl} for the equivalent material determined by the correspondence relations with additional arbitrary terms, the varying elastic moduli are determined by Eq. (19).

A particular choice of the arbitrary terms was retained in the present study based on the following rules. From a theoretical point of view, these constants must preserve the positive definiteness of the quadratic form ϕ_2 but do not affect the results, however, from the numerical point of view they must be neither too large nor too small, not to induce numerical difficulties. Consequently a good choice is to take them of the size of the moduli of the real material. Taking :

$$\begin{aligned} D_{\alpha\beta\beta} &= d_{\alpha\beta}/(3h) \\ D_{\alpha\beta\beta} &= 0 \\ A_{3333} &= A \quad B_{3333} = 0 \quad D_{3333} = A/3 \end{aligned} \quad (24)$$

in which A is the mean value in the thickness of the modulus C_{3333} of the real material, gives the following values for the constants of the equivalent material :

$$\left\{ \begin{aligned} C_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta}^1 &= 12/h^3 D_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta}^M + 18/(\sqrt{15} h^2) B_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta}^M \\ C_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta}^2 &= 9/(4h) A_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta}^M - 15/h^3 D_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta}^M \\ C_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta}^3 &= 12/h^3 D_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta}^M - 18/(\sqrt{15} h^2) B_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta}^M \end{aligned} \right. \quad (25)$$

$$C_{\alpha\beta\beta}^1 = C_{\alpha\beta\beta}^2 = C_{\alpha\beta\beta}^3 = d_{\alpha\beta}^M/h \quad (26)$$

$$C_{\alpha\beta\beta\beta}^1 = C_{\alpha\beta\beta\beta}^2 = C_{\alpha\beta\beta\beta}^3 = 0 \quad (27)$$

$$C_{3333}^1 = C_{3333}^2 = C_{3333}^3 = A \quad (28)$$

It can be seen from these equations that the choice retained in Eq. (24) gives constant moduli (i.e. $C_{ijkl}^1 = C_{ijkl}^2 = C_{ijkl}^3$) in the special case of a homogeneous material, and symmetrical moduli (i.e. $C_{ijkl}^1 = C_{jikl}^1$) for a laminated or sandwich structure without coupling of the in-plane and out-of-plane effects.

IMPLEMENTATION IN THE FINITE

ELEMENT METHOD

The present method was developed for use in the finite element method and was applied to two types of finite elements using numerical integration. One is a three dimensional element of the type shown in Fig. 1, with variable shape and number of nodes which was previously modified to solve homogeneous plate & shell problems [6]. The other is the Ahmad element [7], which is a modified three dimensional element. Both were available for completely anisotropic homogeneous materials and use Gauss-Legendre numerical integration in the three directions with the choice of the number of the Gauss points.

Numerical integration is particularly suitable to the application of the method. It is well known that the stiffness matrix of an element is obtained by an integral over the volume of the element, which is of form :

$$\iiint \mathbf{B}^T \mathbf{D} \mathbf{B} \, dV \quad (29)$$

which can be computed first by an integration along the thickness :

$$\int \mathbf{B}^T \mathbf{D} \mathbf{B} \, dx_3 = h/2 \int_{-1}^{+1} \mathbf{B}^T(z) \mathbf{D}(z) \mathbf{B}(z) dz \quad (30)$$

followed by an integration over the surface delimited in middle plane by the element. We shall pay attention to the integration along the thickness as there is no special feature in the integration over the surface which can be performed following the classical rules of the finite element method.

Turning to the integral of Eq. 30, it is easily seen that the quantities to be integrated are at most of the fifth degree in the variable z , because the strain shape function matrix \mathbf{B} is of the first degree and the elasticity matrix \mathbf{D} formed with the quadratic moduli C_{ijkl} is of the second degree. Consequently, when using the Gauss-Legendre quadrature for the integration along the thickness, it is necessary to select the *three point formula* which gives exact integration up to the fifth degree.

With the form retained for the quadratic variation along the thickness of the elasticity constants C_{ijkl} (i.e. a sum of three terms, each of them contributing only at one of the Gauss points), the integral of Eq. 30 reduces to the sum of three terms:

$$\int \mathbf{B}^T \mathbf{D} \mathbf{B} \, dx_3 = h/2 \left[\mathbf{B}^T(\beta) \mathbf{D}^1 \mathbf{B}(\beta) + \mathbf{B}^T(0) \mathbf{D}^2 \mathbf{B}(0) + \mathbf{B}^T(-\beta) \mathbf{D}^3 \mathbf{B}(-\beta) \right] \quad (31)$$

formula which shows the advantage of the form taken in Eq.(13).

The element subroutines were modified to read the three values of the elasticity matrix \mathbf{D} and the three point Gauss Legendre integration in the z direction was selected. This is only a small alteration of the programs which were consequently adapted very easily.

APPLICATIONS OF THE

METHOD

To assess the validity of the method, it was applied to various test cases which were computed with three finite element programs : (a) the three dimensional element, (b) the modified (Ahmad) three dimensional element, (c) a special program based on the direct analysis of laminated and sandwich plates [7], [8].

Six test cases were studied. They concern clamped square plates under uniformly distributed transverse load. The plates are orthotropic or non orthotropic, of laminated or sandwich structure, with or without coupling between bending and extension. Two materials are used :

- the *ply material* is an orthotropic composite made of epoxy resin reinforced with unidirectional graphite fibres, with the following engineering constants and stiffnesses :

$$\begin{aligned} E_{11} &= 175 \cdot 10^9 \text{ Pa} & E_{22} &= E_{33} = 7 \cdot 10^9 \text{ Pa} \\ G_{12} &= G_{13} = 3.5 \cdot 10^9 \text{ Pa} & G_{23} &= 1.4 \cdot 10^9 \text{ Pa} \\ \nu_{12} &= \nu_{13} = \nu_{23} & &= 0.25 \\ C_{1111} &= 1.761 \, 745 \cdot 10^{11} \text{ Pa} & C_{1122} &= C_{1133} = 2.348 \, 993 \cdot 10^9 \text{ Pa} \\ C_{2233} &= 1.897 \, 987 \cdot 10^9 \text{ Pa} & C_{2222} &= C_{3333} = 7.497 \, 987 \cdot 10^9 \text{ Pa} \\ C_{1212} &= C_{1313} = 3.5 \cdot 10^9 \text{ Pa} & C_{2323} &= 1.4 \cdot 10^9 \text{ Pa} \end{aligned}$$

- the *core material* is a honeycomb epoxy fiberglass material, with the following engineering constants and stiffnesses :

$$\begin{aligned}
 E_{11} &= E_{22} = 0.28 \cdot 10^9 \text{ Pa} & E_{33} &= 3.5 \cdot 10^9 \text{ Pa} \\
 G_{12} &= 0.112 \cdot 10^9 \text{ Pa} & G_{13} &= G_{23} = 0.42 \cdot 10^9 \text{ Pa} \\
 \nu_{12} &= 0.25 & \nu_{13} &= \nu_{23} = 0.02 \\
 C_{1111} &= C_{2222} = .301 \ 189 \ 2 \cdot 10^9 \text{ Pa} & C_{1122} &= .077 \ 189 \ 19 \cdot 10^9 \text{ Pa} \\
 C_{1133} &= C_{2233} = .094 \ 594 \ 59 \cdot 10^9 \text{ Pa} & C_{3333} &= 3.547 \ 297 \cdot 10^9 \text{ Pa} \\
 C_{1212} &= .112 \cdot 10^9 \text{ Pa} & C_{1313} &= C_{2323} = .42 \cdot 10^9 \text{ Pa}
 \end{aligned}$$

Case 1 : Orthotropic laminated plate without coupling. This cross-ply laminate is composed of three plies of equal thickness (0.3 mm) with a $|0^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ|$ stacking sequence. The overall dimensions are 200 mm x 200 mm x 0.9 mm . The value of the distributed load is 1000 Pa .

Case 2 : Orthotropic laminated plate without coupling. This cross-ply laminate is composed of 16 plies of equal thickness (0.2 mm) with a $|0^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ/90^\circ|$ symmetric stacking sequence. The overall dimensions are 200 mm x 200 mm x 3.2 mm . The value of the distributed load is 10^5 Pa.

Case 3 : Non orthotropic laminated plate without coupling. This symmetric laminate is composed of three plies of equal thickness (0.3 mm) with a $|45^\circ/0^\circ/45^\circ|$ stacking sequence. The overall dimensions are 200 mm x 200 mm x 0.9 mm . The value of the distributed load is 1000 Pa .

Case 4 : Non orthotropic laminated plate with coupling. This non symmetric laminate is composed of 16 plies of equal thickness (0.2 mm) at $|0^\circ/45^\circ/90^\circ/-45^\circ/0^\circ/45^\circ/90^\circ/-45^\circ/0^\circ/45^\circ/90^\circ/-45^\circ|$. The overall dimensions are 200 mm x 200 mm x 3.2 mm . The value of the distributed load is 10^5 Pa.

Case 5 : Orthotropic sandwich plate without coupling. This symmetric sandwich is composed of a 18 mm thick core and two facings with the same thickness (1 mm) and the same orientation (0°). The overall dimensions are 400 mm x 400 mm x 20 mm . The value of the distributed load is 10^5 Pa.

Case 6 : Non orthotropic sandwich plate with coupling. This sandwich is composed of a 18 mm thick core and two facings of equal thickness (1 mm), the upper one at 0° and the lower one at 60° . The overall dimensions are 400 mm x 400 mm x 20 mm . The value of the distributed load is 10^5 Pa.

These test cases were computed for various meshes, from which extrapolated values were determined. The results of the three programs are in complete agreement, with all the seven digits printed equal. These results are illustrated in Table 3, which gives the common values of the computed and extrapolated deflection at the centre of the plate for the various cases. The extrapolated values are obtained by two studies of convergence with respect to the number of elements and with respect to the number of equations. Only the digits which proved to be significant in both the processes are retained in Table 3.

It should be emphasized that the three-dimensional program does not provide directly the deflection. It gives u_3^+ and u_3^- , from which the deflection u_3^0 is computed from Eq. 9. These quantities u_3^+ , u_3^0 and u_3^- may be different, as in case n° 2 where $u_3^+ = 1.016 \ 436$, $u_3^0 = 1.016 \ 416$, $u_3^- = 1.016 \ 426$ (4 x 4 mesh) and $u_3^+ = 1.073 \ 682$, $u_3^0 = 1.073 \ 661$, $u_3^- = 1.073 \ 672$ (8 x 8 mesh), whereas, in case n° 3, they are equal for the two meshes. The difference between u_3^+ and u_3^- is obviously related to the values of the stiffnesses A_{3333} and $D_{\alpha 3 \beta 3}$ (see Eq. 23), however no clear trend was ob-

served when varying these quantities.

Case number	Mesh	Deflection in mm	Number of equations		
			3D element	Ahmad element	Special element
1	4 x 4	0.319 142	342	285	†
	8 x 8	0.431 470 2	1 638	1 365	†
	16 x 16	0.431 911 1	†	5 910	5 910
	extrapolation	0.432 02	†	†	†
2	4 x 4	1.016 426	342	285	†
	8 x 8	1.073 672	1 638	1 365	†
	16 x 16	1.074 694	†	5 910	5 910
	extrapolation	1.075 0	†	†	†
3	4 x 4	0.352 710 6	342	285	†
	8 x 8	0.654 267 2	†	1 365	1 365
	extrapolation	0.74	†	†	†
4	4 x 4	1.069 126	342	285	†
	8 x 8	1.124 283	†	1 365	1 365
	extrapolation	1.14	†	†	†
5	4 x 4	0.466 832 1	342	285	†
	8 x 8	0.470 093 8	1 638	1 365	†
	16 x 16	0.470 176 4	†	5 910	5 910
	extrapolation	0.470 197	†	†	†
6	4 x 4	1.207 640	342	285	†
	8 x 8	1.230 659	†	1 365	1 365
	extrapolation	1.237	†	†	†

† : not computed

Table 3 - Computed and extrapolated values of the deflection at the centre of the plates.

CONCLUSION

The present paper developed a theoretical analysis demonstrating that an appropriately modified three dimensional isoparametric finite element can be used to solve the equations of equilibrium for the laminated or sandwich structures. This is obtained by using a fictitious *equivalent material*. This equivalent material has elastic stiffnesses with quadratic variation along the thickness of the structure. Apart from non-significant quantities connected only with a superfluous variable, the stiffnesses of the equivalent material are completely determined by the in-plane, bending, coupling and shear stiffnesses of the real structure. This analysis was applied to a complete three dimensional finite element and an Ahmad three dimensional finite element, the results of which were compared with the results of a special laminated and sandwich plate finite element. A complete agreement was obtained in numerous tests from which six are described in this paper. Consequently, it can be concluded that the present study provides a process to convert a classical three dimensional finite element program into an efficient laminated or sandwich finite element program, with only a small, low-cost alteration.

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